

INVESTIGATING THE CUSTOMER BUYING BEHAVIOR OF FABRIC PRODUCTS IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The purpose of this study is to understand the variables affecting the consumers while purchasing the products and to identify whether the purchase of the products creates or disappointment leading to affinity towards handloom products.

Design/Research Methodology/approach: Data were collected from 251 handloom product customers in Bhopal through a questionnaire and collected data is analysed with the help of Percentage analysis and Factor analysis.

Findings: The attitude of the consumers towards handloom products was highly influenced by the attributes of convenience, attraction, expectation and awareness.

Research Implications: The consumers prefer handloom products for their regular use and were of the opinion that their reaction will differ towards price changes of handloom products and hence, the sellers can consider these as the important elements while fixing of the prices of the handloom products.

Scope for future work / Research limitations: This study mainly focused to identify the factors influencing the attitude of the consumers towards purchase of handloom products and also study about the consumer attitude depending on the demographic factors of the handloom product. The consumers attitude may also be assessed by including some more attitudinal factors. Further this contribution surveyed 251 respondents from a particular city; hence the result may or may not be applicable to the other cities or states in India.

Originality/value: The analysis based on secondary data has found that there are various studies on factors affecting consumer attitude but this paper has taken demographic factors affecting consumers purchasing attitude towards handloom products.

Key Words: Demographic factors, factor analysis, customer delight

Paper type: Research paper

INTRODUCTION

While considering the purchase behaviour, one of the most important drivers is the customer attitude. Attitudes exactly reflects the mindset of the consumers whether there is a favourable/ delight or unfavourable / disappointment ultimately inducing consumers either to purchase or not to purchase the particular products or brands. Attitude may be considered as a learning process by way of personal experience, perceived behaviour. Attitude stimulates awareness, loyalty, expectations and convenience leading to purchasing decision. Attitude may transform low-involvement products into high involvement products.

The natural liking of these handloom sarees creates credibility and loyalty towards the other handloom products like dhotis, dress materials, lungies, towels, shirtings, bedsheets,

carpets and rugs, mosquito nets, bathroom/bedding linen, etc., thereby creating a strong social bondage resulting in affinity.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Varghese, S., & John, A. P. ¹(2018), evaluated the factors determining the acceptance of handloom clothing in Bangalore City. The objectives of the study were to assess the awareness level of customers and to identify the barriers limiting the buying decision of handloom clothing. Lack of size options, not multi-functional, no publicity in metropolitan cities, limited availability and limited exhibitions were identified as the barriers limiting the buying decision of handloom clothing. The handloom clothing outlets were not sufficient and not placed at suitable locations. Promotional activities are need to be improved and variety designed clothes for all age groups to be introduced. Gayathri V.Nair and Kinslin D ²(2016) in their study aimed to understand the consumer awareness level and identified the most powerful source of information and occasion which influenced the consumers to buy handloom products at Trivandrum District, Kerala. The customers preferred to buy handloom products during festive occasions and if it is a necessity. Handloom exhibitions was the main source of awareness for handloom products. The pricing policy adopted by the marketers has a significance relationship with the level of satisfaction towards purchase of handloom products. Padmasani, S, Muruganandhan S., & Yazhini M. ³(2012), examined the attitude and satisfaction of rural and urban customers of khadi products among 100 customers in Gobichettipalayam. The attitude of the customers towards khadi products was significantly different on the demographic factors. There was no difference in the attitude among the rural and urban customers towards khadi products with respect to the price, quality, availability, package and customer service. There was a positive relationship between the attitude towards khadi products and satisfaction of customers.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study about the consumer attitude depending on the demographic factors of the handloom product consumers.
2. To identify the factors influencing the attitude of the consumers towards purchase of handloom products.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is based on primary data which has been collected from the users of various handloom products by a well-designed questionnaire. Questionnaires were distributed to 251 respondents chosen through convenience sampling. Research tools used for the empirical study was scaled questionnaire inclusive of 5-point Likert Scale [strongly agree with 5 to strongly disagree with 1] and close ended questions. For analysis of the data, SPSS V.21 was used. The secondary data was collected from various journals, newspapers and website sources.

DEMOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS

The purchase attitude of the consumers as regards handloom products depends on the demographic variables.

Table No. 1: Demographic Profile and Purchase attitude of the respondents

Variable	Dominant Group	Percentage
Gender	Female	79.54
Age (in years)	20-30	67.56
Educational Qualification	Undergraduate	61.53
Marital Status	Unmarried	74.01
Occupational Status	Student	59.51
Household income (p.m.)	Below Rs.20,000	27.03
Years of interest to purchase handloom products	Up to 1 year	45.55
Source of information [Sales personnel, advertisement, Friends & relatives, trade fairs/ exhibitions]	All Sources	34.04
Person influencing the purchase decision	Self	45.53
Preference to buy for [friends, family members, themself]	For all	48.04
Opinion towards eco-friendliness	High	52.00
Ranking of the handloom products	Good	33.51
Reaction towards price changes	Opinion to buy will differ	71.56
Product Preference	Sarees	34.07
Preference for regular use	Handloom products	71.54

Source: Questionnaire

FACTOR ANALYSIS

Factor analysis has been applied to investigate the underlying structure of the variables that influence the attitude of the consumers in building affinity towards the purchase of handloom products. The Cronbach's Alpha value of total variables is 0.888 which is more consistent hence the set of questions chosen for the study was reliable. KMO measure of sampling adequacy was 0.883 and Bartlett's test showed a significance of .000. Therefore, factor analysis could be applied to 18 variables measuring the attitude of consumers towards purchase of the handloom products. The anti-image matrices of variables measuring the attitude of consumers towards purchase of handloom products was calculated and it was observed that all measures of sampling adequacy (MSA) being more than 0.5, all the 18 variables could be subjected to factor analysis.

Table No.2 :Attributes of Consumers' Attitude in Respective Factors

S. No.	Attributes	Variables	Factor loadings
Factor 1	Convenience	Reasonable Price	.727
		Outlets are placed in suitable locations	.721
		Many varieties are available	.637
		Trendy designs are available for teenagers	.644

		Many varieties of products available for men	.628
		Colours are sufficient	.616
		Reasonable prices for regular wear and occasional wear	.493
Factor 2	Attraction	Consumption is considered as status quo	.787
		Availability in social media	.678
		Colour combinations are good	.599
		Suitability for all climate	.587
Factor 3	Expectation	Selling outlets for handlooms are comparatively less than other outlets	.774
		Better quality than power loom products	.679
		Special focus on traditional and contemporary design	.597
		Finishing is good	.585
Factor 4	Awareness	Awareness of all the handloom products	.798
		Knowledge about the healthiness of handloom product	.669
		Durability of handloom products	.432
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis			
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization			

Table 3 shows that Principal Component Method of Factor Analysis and the Varimax Rotation Method has been used to group the 18 Variables into 4 factors. The most dominant factor is ‘Convenience’ and it includes 7 variables viz, reasonable price, outlets at suitable locations, more varieties for all, trendy designs for teenagers, availability of many varieties for men, sufficient colours and reasonable prices offered for regular and occasional wear and it explains 19.368% of the variance. The next factor is ‘Attraction’ which comprises of 4 factors viz., consumption of handloom products is considered as status quo, availability in social media, good colour combinations and suitable for all climate. It explains a variance of 14.301%. The third factor is ‘Expectation’ which comprises of 4 factors viz., need for more selling outlets, better quality requirements, special focus on contemporary and traditional design and good finishing. It explains 12.913% of the variance. The last factor is ‘Awareness’ which comprises of 3 variables viz., awareness about all the handloom products, knowledge about the healthiness of handloom products and its durability. This factor explains 9.618% of the variance.

CONCLUSION

The attitude of the consumers towards handloom products was highly influenced by the attributes of convenience, attraction, expectation and awareness. The consumers prefer handloom products for their regular use and were of the opinion that their reaction will differ towards price changes of handloom products and hence, the sellers can consider these as the important elements while fixing of the prices of the handloom products. The knowledge about the healthiness of handloom products determines the favourable attitude (delight), leading to affinity towards the purchase of handloom products.

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